

Extraction of copper(II) from sodium salicylate medium using neutral organo-phosphorus extractant Cyanex-923 in toluene

S. U. Gaikwad and S. D. Pawar*

Department of Chemistry, Siddharth College of Arts, Science and Commerce, Dr. D. N. Road, Fort, Mumbai-400 001, India

E-mail : sureshpawar_2004@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-22-22819049

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Abstract : The neutral extractant Cyanex-923 has been used for the extraction of Cu^{II} from sodium salicylate medium. This metal ion was found to be quantitatively extracted with Cyanex-923 in toluene at pH 6 and from the organic phase it is stripped with 3 M HCl solution. The effect of pH, sodium salicylate concentration, reagent concentration, equilibration period, diluents, diverse ions and stripping agent on the extraction of Cu^{II} has been studied. The stoichiometry of the extracted species of this metal ion was determined on the basis of the slope analysis method. The reaction proceeds by solvation and the probable extracted species found was $\text{Cu}(\text{HSal})_2 \cdot 2 \text{Cyanex-923}$.

Keywords : Extraction, Cyanex-923, toluene, sodium salicylate.

Introduction

Extraction behavior of Cu^{II} with new extractants have been studied using extractants like 8-(alkyl phenyl sulfonamido)pyridine, 2-(alkyl phenyl sulfonamido methyl)thiophene, 2-(alkyl phenyl sulfonamido)-benzothiazolethiazole, 2-(alkyl phenyl sulfonamido)-thiazole¹. Solvent extraction of several divalent metal ion like Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cd^{II} in 0.1 M NaNO_3 solution was carried out using benzoyl trifluoroacetone and 2-thionyl trifluoroacetone in chloroform². Recently Acorga M5640³, Alamine 336-LIX54⁴, Alamine 336⁵ and LIX 973N⁶ are employed for the extraction of copper³. Uptake of Zn^{II} and Cu^{II} from acid aqueous solution was studied using micro capsules containing 2-ethylhexyl phosphonic acid mono 2-ethyl hexyl ester⁷. Heap leaching of oxide of copper ore and cathode copper recovery was investigated by solvated extraction (SX) and electro winning (EW) method⁸. Reduction of Cu^{II} during solvent extraction as thiocyanate complexes into 4-methyl-2-pentanone⁹ was also carried out. Solvent extraction of Cu^{II} from 0.1 M sulphate medium and kinetic studies using single drop method was performed using bis-(2,4,4-trimethylpentyl)phosphinic and phosphonic acid^{10,11}. Competitive bulk liquid membrane transported extraction of Cu^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} and Mn^{II} cations using 5-methyl-4

(thiophen-2-yl-methylene amino)-3-thio-oxo-1,2,4-triazol-5-one and phthalic dicarboxaldehyde is also studied¹².

However no work was carried out for the extraction of Cu^{II} from salicylate media using Cyanex-923 in toluene. The proposed methods were then employed for the analysis of Cu^{II} in alloy samples like tin based white metal and commercial nickel.

Apparatus and reagent :

The extractant Cyanex-923 supplied by Cytec Industries Inc., Canada was used without further purification. A known amount of Cu^{II} sulphate pentahydrate was dissolved in minimum quantity of sulphuric acid and diluted to 1 L with double distilled water. All other chemical used were of analytical grade. EQUIP-TRONIC model EQ-614 pH meter with combined electrode was used for H^+ ions concentration studies and ELICO UV-Visible SL-27 spectrophotometer with 10 mm cortex quartz cuvettes for absorbance measurement.

Procedure :

A 10 ml aliquot of sample containing 20 μg of Cu^{II} and 0.002 M of sodium salicylate was equilibrated with an equal volume of 0.1 M Cyanex-923 in toluene for 10 min, after adjusting their aqueous solution pH to 6.0 with dilute HCl and NH_3 . The metal loaded organic phase was

back-extracted with 3 M HCl and was determined spectrophotometrically by the 4-(2-pyridylazo)resorcinol (PAR)¹³ method at 540 nm. The pH of the Cu^{II} solution containing 1 ml of 0.1% (PAR) is adjusted to 2.0, diluted to 25 ml and absorbance is measured at 540 nm. All the experiments were carried out at room temperature.

Results and discussion

Effect of pH :

Extraction of Cu^{II} containing 0.002 M sodium salicylate was carried out in the pH range of 1.0–7.0 with Cyanex-923 diluted with toluene. With the increase in pH, the extraction increased and found to be quantitative at pH 6.0. Hence all the extraction of Cu^{II} with Cyanex-923 were carried out at a fixed pH of 6.0.

Effect of sodium salicylate :

The effect of sodium salicylate concentration on the percentage extraction of Cu^{II} with 0.1 M Cyanex-923 in toluene was studied in the sodium salicylate range from 2.5×10^{-4} – 2.5×10^{-3} M. Increasing sodium salicylate concentration increased the extraction and became optimum in the range 2×10^{-3} – 2.5×10^{-3} M. Hence all the extractions were carried out at 0.002 M sodium salicylate with Cyanex-923.

Effect of reagent concentration :

Extraction of Cu^{II} was also carried out by varying the reagent concentration (1.0×10^{-2} – 1.0×10^{-1} M) while keeping other parameters like pH, period of equilibration, diluent and temperature constant. Extraction was found to increase with increase in reagent concentration. The distribution ratio increases with increase in reagent concentration. The extraction of Cu^{II} was quantitative at 0.1 M Cyanex-923 in toluene, hence all the extractions of Cu^{II} were carried at fixed reagent concentration of 0.1 M.

Effect of diluents and period of equilibration :

Various aromatic and aliphatic diluents like toluene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, cyclohexane, *n*-hexane and xylene were employed for extraction of Cu^{II}. The extraction of Cu^{II} with Cyanex-923 was found to be quantitative in all diluents except chloroform (89.6%). Toluene was used as best diluent for Cyanex-923 extractant because of better phase separation. Extraction equilibrium was studied for different periods of shaking ranging from 1–30 min. It was observed that 10 min of shaking period was sufficient for quantitative extraction of Cu^{II} with 0.1 M Cyanex-923 in toluene. However there was no adverse effect by increasing the extraction period upto 30 min.

Effect of various stripping agents :

Cu^{II} was stripped out from its metal loaded organic phases with different strength of mineral acids like HCl, HNO₃, H₂SO₄. It was found that quantitative stripping of Cu^{II} from the organic phase was observed at 3–4 M HCl, 3–4 M HNO₃ and 4 M H₂SO₄ (Table 1).

Table 1. Effect of stripping agents on percentage recovery of Cu^{II} = 20 µg

Acids Molarity (M)	Percentage recovery of Cu ^{II} from metal loaded organic phase of Cyanex-923 in toluene, with strippants		
	HCl	H ₂ SO ₄	HNO ₃
1.0	75.8	60.4	86.7
2.0	91.7	75.0	99.9
3.0	99.9	91.7	99.9
4.0	99.9	99.9	99.9

Composition of extracted species :

It was necessary to evaluate the distribution coefficient (*D*) while varying the extractant concentration to ascertain the nature of extracted species. The composition of the extracted species was first ascertained from graph of log *D* versus log *R* at fixed pH of 6.0. The slope obtained was 1.92 indicating that two mole of Cyanex-923 react with one mole of copper ion. The slope of the plot of log *D* versus log [HSaly⁻] is 1.9 suggesting that two mole of salicylate ion are used up in the process. The probable compositions of the extractable species of Cu^{II} with Cyanex-923 is 1 : 2 and the probable extracted species is Cu(HSal)₂ · 2 Cyanex-923.

Effect of diverse ions :

The effect of various diverse ions on the extraction of Cu^{II} was studied with Cyanex-923 in toluene. The tolerance limit of individual foreign ions was set so that error in recovery was not more than ±2%.

It was found that EDTA and disodiumtartrate interfered badly while alkali and alkaline earth metals like Na^I, Li^I, K^I, Mg^{II} are tolerated upto 20 times to Cu^{II}. The other ions like Cl⁻, Br⁻, SO₃²⁻, I⁻, S²⁻, NO₃⁻, ClO₄⁻ interfered in the ratio 1 : 50, Mn^{II}, V^V, Cr^{III}, Fe^{III}, Ni^{II}, Hg^{II}, Co^{II}, Pb^{II} in the ratio 1 : 10, Ti^{IV}, Cd^{II}, Rb^I, Ag^I in the ratio 1 : 5 and Ga^{III}, Be^{II}, Al^{III}, Ti^{III}, Zn^{II} in the ratio 1 : 3.

Influence of temperature :

Extraction of Cu^{II} with 0.1 M Cyanex-923 in toluene at 0.002 M sodium salicylate concentration at pH 3.0 was carried out at different temperatures (upto 343 K). The

distribution ratio decreased with increase in temperature. As per the Van't Hoff equation, $\log D_{\text{Cu}} = -(\Delta H/2.303RT) + C$, where D_{Cu} represent the distribution ratio, ΔH is the enthalpy change for the reaction and C is the constant.

The slopes obtained from the linear plot of $\log D_{\text{Cu}}$ vs $1000/T$ was 1.58. The ΔH values calculated was $-30.25 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ indicating that the extraction reaction of Cu^{II} with Cyanex-923 is exothermic in nature.

Analysis of sample :

The proposed methods were employed for the analysis of Cu^{II} in alloy samples like tin based white metal and commercial nickel¹³. A 100 mg of each alloy was dissolved in 15 ml of nitric acid and evaporated to dryness. The residue was treated with water and precipitated metastannic acid was filtered and then washed with hot dilute nitric acid and water. The filtrates, thus obtained were diluted to 25 ml. An aliquots of these filtrates were analyzed for copper by the proposed method described above. The percentage recovery of copper by the above method in the tin based white metal and commercial nickel is 99.2% and 99.3% respectively (Table 2).

Table 2. Analysis of copper in alloys

Samples	Extraction with Cyanex-923 in toluene		%Recovery	R.S.D.
	Present	Found		
	(mg)	(mg)		
Tin base white metal (BCS 178)	4.58	4.54	99.2	0.22
Commercial nickel	0.39	0.37	99.3	0.21

Conclusion :

The commercially available phosphine oxide, Cyanex-923 in toluene can be employed for the extraction of Cu^{II} quantitatively from salicylate medium at pH 6.

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